

THE EFFECT OF EXTERNAL MECHANICAL LOADING ON THE CHANGE OF
THE MATRIX RESIDUAL STRESSES IN SiC/Al COMPOSITES

N. Shi and R.J. Arsenault
Metallurgical Materials Laboratory
University of Maryland
College Park, Maryland 20742 USA

ABSTRACT

The change of the average matrix residual stress as a function of two particular kinds of simple loading history was investigated, i.e. tension and compression. The major factor which controls the pattern of the change is presented.

INTRODUCTION

Previous experimental investigations of the deformation behavior of the short fiber reinforced SiC/Al composites have indicated that the constitutive behavior of these composites is distinctly different under applied uniaxial compressive and tensile loadings. It is generally found that the compressive yield strength of these composites is larger than that of the tensile yield strength while the Young's modulus for compression is smaller than that in tension^{1,2}. It has been pointed out by various researchers¹⁻⁴ that the differences in response of the SiC/Al composite material to tensile or compressive load is closely related to the matrix thermal residual stresses. The previous analytical and experimental results indicate that in whisker reinforced composites the average thermal residual stress in the loading direction (z) in the matrix is in tension^{2,4}. However, the change of residual stresses which may be a principal factor that affects the flow properties of the composites as a function of applied load has not been reported in the literature. It is therefore the primary goal of this investigation to analytically evaluate such a change in the magnitude of the matrix residual stresses. Throughout the analysis, it is understood that the term "residual stress" is referring to the phrase "the average matrix residual stress in loading direction Z."

FINITE ELEMENT (FEM) MODELING PROCEDURES

In our previous research⁵, it was shown that a two-dimensional FEM model could qualitatively reproduce the changes in characteristic constitutive and flow properties of the whisker reinforced SiC/Al composites when the system is subject to either a uniaxial tensile or compressive loading. Based on the assumption that the change of the flow properties are largely controlled by the change in residual stresses, it is also conceivable that the change of residual stress can be qualitatively predicted.

In the present residual stress analysis, the ADINA finite element analysis code was used. The parameters used in this simulation correspond to annealed 6061 aluminum reinforced by SiC whiskers. The samples were initially thermally treated by setting a zero stress state at 773 K and then cooling down to 293 K and loaded either in

tension or compression to determine the materials' response under the influence of the thermal residual stresses. Such a response is characterized by macroscopically generating stress-strain curves which can be compared with experimental curves⁵ and microscopically analyzing the change of the residual stresses after the external load is removed.

The composites are assumed to be two-dimensional infinite array of hexagonal packed parallelepipeds imbedded into the matrix. If the volume fraction of whisker is constant, it has been shown⁵ that a small variation in interparticle spacing will not greatly affect the material's property. Therefore, in the subsequent analysis, the interparticle spacing was not selected as a critical parameter.

In the current analysis, 20V% SiC whisker composites with whisker aspect ratio equal to 4 were investigated. A multi-constraint boundary condition was employed so that only a quadrant of the material which contains the SiC whisker, as shown in Fig. 1, was considered to represent the whole infinite array.

Fig. 1 Diagram of the composite unit cell for FEM calculation where the shaded area represents a quadrant of the SiC whisker and the remainder is Al.

RESIDUAL STRESS ANALYSIS

The average matrix residual stress is obtained in such a way that the stress values generated by FEM were averaged over the entire volume of the matrix. It was found that the average matrix residual stress along the tensile axes will drop initially and then will increase or decrease depending on the nature of the external loading (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 A prediction of the change in the average thermal residual stress as function of external strain. C.F. is for initially tested in compression and T.F. is for tested in tension first.

Fig. 3 Schematic diagram of the thermal residual stress arrangement where compressive residual stress is at the end of the fiber and the rest of the matrix is under tension.

and Fig. 3 shows a schematic of the thermal residual stress arrangement where at the whisker end the matrix is under compression while the rest of the matrix is under tension.

THEORETICAL EVALUATION OF THE CHANGE OF RESIDUAL STRESS UPON EXTERNAL LOADING

In this section, an analytical investigation was undertaken in order to obtain a physical understanding as to why there is an asymmetrical behavior due to plastic straining, i.e. compressive loading is not a mirror image of the tensile loading^{1,3}. It was intended to depict the actual main physical process through the simplest model possible.

It is the authors' belief that the effect of the volume mismatch between the SiC particle and the Al matrix should be responsible for the asymmetric behaviors of the composites. Therefore, a simple discontinuous composite model based on such an idea was developed. It is assumed that a piece of SiC whisker is embedded into Al matrix, as shown in Fig. 1, except there is no bonding between SiC and Al along the whisker axes. Thus, there would be no shear load transfer and the boundary between tension and the compression zone is assumed to be the extension of SiC/Al interface along the whisker axes. Moreover, the shear stress at the zone boundary is assumed to be negligible. Also, a multi-constraint type of boundary condition was adopted as in the FEM analysis.

By following the same physical cooling and the subsequent mechanical loading process as described in the previous FEM section, the thermal residual stress can be determined as:

For the case of tension first:

$$\begin{cases} \sigma_{wR} = \sigma_{Ym} + \frac{E_w E_{mT}}{F_C E_w + F_w E_{mT}} \epsilon_{cp} - \frac{E_m E_w}{F_C E_w + F_w E_m} \frac{\sigma_C}{E_C} \\ \sigma_{mR} = - \frac{1 - V_T}{V_T} \sigma_{wR} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

For the case of compression first:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \sigma_{wR} = \frac{-V_t}{1-V_t} \sigma_{mR_T} + \frac{E_w E_{mT}}{F_C E_w + F_w E_{mT}} \epsilon_{Total}^A - \frac{E_m E_w}{F_C E_w + F_w E_m} \frac{\sigma_C}{E_C} \\ \sigma_{mR} = -\frac{1-V_T}{V_T} \sigma_{wR} \end{array} \right. \quad (2)$$

In both Eq. 1 and Eq. 2, σ_{wR} and σ_{mR} represent the residual stress in loading direction in the whisker and matrix, respectively. E_w and E_m are the Young's modulus for the whisker and matrix, E_{mT} is the work hardening rate for the matrix, α_w and α_m are the coefficients of thermal expansion for the whisker and matrix. σ_{Y_m} is the yield stress for the matrix, and E_C is the all-elastic Young's modulus of the composite without thermal residual stress as opposed to the apparent composite Young's modulus in which part of the matrix started plastically deforming right at the beginning of the loading

$$E_C = \frac{(1-V_T) E_m E_w}{F_C E_w + F_w E_m} + V_T E_m \quad (3)$$

where V_T is the volume fraction of the tension zone, and

$$F_C = \frac{V_C^2 V_w}{V_w + V_C} \quad F_w = \frac{V_C V_w^2}{V_w + V_C} \quad (4)$$

V_C and V_w are the volume fractions of compression zone and SiC whisker, respectively. Furthermore, σ_{mR_T} is the thermal residual stress in the tension zone. When ΔT is large enough to have induced plasticity which is true for the SiC/Al system^{6,7}

$$\sigma_{mR_T} = \frac{F_w (\alpha_w - \alpha_m) \Delta T + \sigma_{Y_m} F_w \left(\frac{1}{E_{mT}} - \frac{1}{E_m} \right)}{\left[\frac{1}{E_{mT}} + F_C \frac{V_T}{1-V_T} \frac{1}{E_{mT}} + F_w \frac{V_T}{(1-V_T)} \frac{1}{E_w} \right]} \quad (5)$$

and the average matrix residual stress ($\bar{\sigma}_m$) will be

$$\bar{\sigma}_m = \sigma_{mR} V_T \frac{F_w}{1-V_w} \quad (6)$$

Fig. 4 A comparison between FEM and analytical results of average residual stress as function of total strain.

Fig. 4 shows the schematic curve for Eq. (6) if Eqs. 1 and 2 are considered.

DISCUSSION

From a consideration of Fig. 4, it is clear that the discontinuous composite model gives good qualitative agreement with the FEM data on the slope of the change of the residual stress. To be more specific, not only that the average residual stress drop is evident, but the slope change can also be correctly predicted. To understand the underlying mechanism for the change in residual stress, it is helpful to define a term as average matrix effective stress ($\bar{\sigma}_{m\text{eff}}$) based on a weighted averaging scheme where an expression for the loading rate $(\partial\sigma_z/\partial p)^2$ may be used as a weighting function, where σ_z is the stress component in the loading direction corresponding to applied load p . Reevaluating the FEM results in the previous section by this scheme, it can be found that the ratio of the average matrix residual stress over the average effective residual stress ($\bar{\sigma}_m/\bar{\sigma}_{m\text{eff}}$) is greater than $[(\bar{\sigma}_m/\bar{\sigma}_{m\text{eff}})|_{p=0} = 1.55]$. This simply means that in order to maintain the volume compatibility, the compression zone at the whisker end will respond faster than the rest of the matrix, i.e. higher stress (strain) rate. This local stress (strain) rate inhomogeneity will later alter the residual stress arrangement after unloading.

Furthermore, it is worthwhile to point out that in the case of compression first, there is a sign change in slope $\partial\sigma_m/\partial\epsilon^A_{Total}$ after the

composite starts yielding, which is predicted by both FEM and the discontinuous composite model. This is an indication that the interaction between tension and the compression zone becomes totally different. Once the macro-yielding is observed, a fact which has to be considered is that the matrix material is deforming plastically throughout regardless of initial sign of the residual stress. It is also interesting to point out that while the tendency of residual stress change is agreeable with both FEM and discontinuous composite model, the actual magnitude of the residual stresses predicted by the analytical model is much smaller than that predicted by the FEM. It is speculated that the absence of interfacial bonding in the model is

the key reason for the discrepancy. This discrepancy may be solved by assuming a set of effective materials' constant to the matrix material near the interface (tension zone).

CONCLUSION

In summary, (1) the predicted change of the average residual stress is asymmetrical, i.e. regardless of sign of the loading, the magnitude of the average residual stress drops upon initial elastic deformation, and it will increase or decrease depending on whether the loading history is compressive or tensile, and (2) the change of the residual stress predicted by FEM is generally comparable to that predicted by the theoretical model which is based on the volume mismatch between the reinforcement and the matrix. This indicates that such volume incompatibility is the controlling factor to the change of the residual stress.

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